

Exploring the Professional Trajectories of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduates of San Isidro College: An In-Depth Tracer Study

Aurence Nichole B. Hallasgo ^{1a}, MBA & Evan P. Taja-on, MSc ^{2b}

¹School of Business Administration, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, 8700

²School of Education, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, 8700

✉ ^aanhallasgo@sic.edu.ph, ^betajaon@sic.edu.ph

How to cite this paper:

Hallasgo, A.N. & Taja-on, E. (2023)
Exploring the Professional Trajectories of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduates of San Isidro College: An In-Depth Tracer Study. *School of Education Research Journal*, 4(1), 152-166.

Received: July 24, 2023
Accepted: October 25, 2023
Published: December 29, 2023

Copyright © 2022 by authors and School of Education Research Journal.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

The tracer study for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) degree with Business Economics (BE), Financial Management (FM), Human Resource Management (HRM), and Marketing Management (MM) of the School of Business Administration (SBA) tracks and gathers information about the career outcomes and experiences of graduates of the degree program. This study focuses on determining the employment opportunities pursued by the graduates of 2018–2022, as well as exploring the influence their education from the SBA of San Isidro College (SIC) has had on their careers. Through this tracer study, valuable insight has been gained into the effectiveness of the SBA's BSBA program offered by SIC and its graduates' overall success and impact in the job market. The lack of respondents in the BE major suggests a need to revisit and modify the curriculum and marketing efforts to generate more interest among potential students. The FM, HRM, and MM major should be capitalized and sustained to maintain the positive momentum. The study's findings show a mix of employment outcomes for graduates, with opportunities for both early career growth and long-term employment. The program equips graduates with a diverse skillset for various job levels and industries. Most graduates find employment within the province, implying effectiveness in equipping them with the necessary skills. However, the distribution of salaries suggests potential issues with the job market or degree value, requiring further investigation. The program has successfully developed graduates with communication, human relations, and entrepreneurial skills but may need improvement in marketing management, problem-solving, and critical thinking. The study concludes that graduates have higher

communication skills but lower problem-solving and critical thinking skills, emphasizing the need for curriculum modifications and additional support to improve overall skills.

Subject Area

Tracer Study

Keywords: *Tracer Study; BSBA Graduates; Career Path*

INTRODUCTION

A tracer study is used to track and follow up on the progress of the institution's alums after graduation. It involves collecting data on graduates' employment status, job satisfaction, income, and job-related skills (Tadlas, 2021). It is necessary to conduct a tracer study to evaluate the program's effectiveness, identify areas of improvement, and provide feedback to the institution to improve the quality of education and career preparation for future graduates. It also helps to ensure the program's relevance to the current job market and industry demands (Hazaymeh & Dela Peña, 2017).

The researchers' study is used to track the career and employment paths of graduates of Bachelor of Business Administration (BSBA) under the School of Business Administration (SBA) of San Isidro College (SIC). It aims to help understand the effectiveness of their educational programs and the outcomes (Pentang et al., 2022). The tracer study is particularly crucial for higher education institutions (HEIs) because they are designed to track and analyze the career paths and experiences of the SIC SBA graduates. This enables SIC SBA to evaluate the relevance and quality of the academic programs and make informed decisions on curriculum design and modifications. It also helps SIC SBA to build strong relationships with industry partners and foster collaboration to serve better their students' future employment prospects (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020).

Tracking the career path for a tracer study enables researchers to determine the extent to which an institution's graduates have been successful in their respective fields of study. This, in turn, provides valuable information to the institution in evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of its academic programs, identifying areas for improvement, and making data-driven decisions that can enhance the employability of its graduates (Cuadra et al., 2019). Many accrediting bodies require educational institutions to demonstrate the quality and relevance of their programs through a tracer study. It allows institutions to provide evidence of the employability and success of their graduates, ensuring the degree meets the necessary standards (Badiru & Wahome, 2016).

This tracer study aims to track the employment outcomes and career paths of BSBA graduates after they have received their degrees. This research aims to evaluate the program's effectiveness in preparing graduates for the job market and identify areas for improvement. The tracer study results can provide valuable information for the college institution to adjust its curriculum and improve its program to meet the demands of the job market.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The tracer study aims to track the outcomes of the School of Business Administration (SBA) graduates in terms of employment or other relevant measures of success. The study anchors on the

concept of quality assurance, which is critical in making informed decisions regarding program improvement or resource allocation. Quality assurance is essential for the tracer study as it ensures the accuracy and validity of the data collected, which is necessary for informed decision-making and optimizing program outcomes (Badiru & Wahome, 2016). Figure 1 displays the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1.
Conceptual Framework of the Study

Conducting a tracer study for graduates of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) is vital because it helps assess the employability and job prospects of graduates after completion of their program. Through this study, the school and educators could understand the demand for the program in the labor market and make informed decisions regarding program structure and curriculum (Cuadra et al., 2019). Moreover, the employability of graduates is critical to the success of this tracer study, as it helps to determine the quality of education received by graduates of the BSBA program. This study evaluates how well graduates have acquired skills that employers need and examines their program's relevance to the current labor market (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020).

Furthermore, the tracer study for BSBA graduates focuses on assessing the skills and knowledge they acquired during their program and how they can be used in the workforce. These skills include communication, human relations, entrepreneurial, marketing management, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills, which employers highly value and seek. By evaluating these skills, the tracer study helps educators understand how to improve the curriculum or programs and help graduates become more competitive in the job market (Dotong et al., 2016).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study sought to discover what paths were taken by graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program from the Academic Years 2018–2022 at the School of Business Administration (SBA) and how these findings can contribute to the strengthening of programs at San Isidro College (SIC) in light of K-12 education.

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the evaluation of the BSBA graduates' employment status?
2. What is the rating of the BSBA graduates on their graduate skills?
3. What are the graduate's suggestions to help improve the curriculum of the BSBA program?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used a descriptive research design to ascertain the tracer study. The study used a descriptive survey covering the Business Administration graduates from 2018–2022 San Isidro College (SIC). The study employed purposive sampling methods to obtain the relevant information from the graduates of the Business Administration program.

The research adopted the research questionnaire by Tadlas (2021) and recalibrated it to suit the needs of the study. The questionnaire comprised the respondents' profile, employment profile, competencies, and skills learned from the course curriculum, and a space was provided for the respondents' suggestions to help improve the course curriculum. The competency and skills reflect the graduates' skills in communication, human relations, entrepreneurial, marketing management, problem-solving, and critical thinking with the criteria using the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
5	4.21 – 5.00	An excellent extent
4	3.41 – 4.20	A great extent
3	2.61 – 3.40	A moderate extent
2	1.81 – 2.60	To some extent
1	1.00 – 1.80	A little or no extent

Three (3) months were spent on the data-gathering procedure through Google Forms and actual surveys. As presented in Table 1, the graduates for the Academic Years of 2018–2022 totaled 123 individuals with different majors in Business Economics (BE), Financial Management (FM), Human Resource Management (HRM), and Marketing Management (MM).

Table 1.

Graduate respondents of from the Academic Years of 2018–2022.

Academic Year	No. of Graduates	No. of Respondents	%
2017–2018	17	12	70.59
2018–2019	24	17	70.83
2019–2020	36	21	58.33
2020–2021	31	22	70.97
2021–2022	16	7	43.75
TOTAL	123	79	64.23

Based on Table 1, from the total of 123 graduates, 79 (64.23%) graduates participated in the study. Most of the participants are from 2018, 2019, and 2021 graduates.

Table 2 presents the distribution of the graduate's profile regarding sex, civil status, course major, and graduation year.

Table 2.
Demographic profile of the respondents (N=79)

Demographic Profile		<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Male	38	48.10
	Female	41	51.90
Civil Status	Single	34	43.04
	Married	45	56.96
Course Major	Business Economics	0	0.00
	Financial Management	27	34.18
	Human Resource Management	31	39.24
	Marketing Management	21	26.58
Year of Graduation	2018	12	15.19
	2019	17	21.52
	2020	21	26.58
	2021	22	27.85
	2022	7	8.86

Based on Table 2, the study's respondents, male and female, are fairly represented and mostly married. None of the respondents who participated in the tracer study were business economics majors. A considerable number of graduates are financial management majors. A significant portion of graduates are human resource majors. A notable number of graduates are marketing majors. Most of the participants are graduates from 2021, 2020, and 2019, while the rest have a percentage lower than 20%.

All the responses of the graduates were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted. The quantitative data was treated using descriptive statistics, specifically mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage. ANOVA was used to compare the graduates' competency and skills. The qualitative data was treated using thematic analysis by identifying common topics and ideas from the graduates' responses. The graduates were informed and oriented on the importance of their evaluation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study traced the graduates of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) under the School of Business Administration (SBA) of San Isidro College (SIC). Data was gathered from the graduates through Google Forms and the actual survey method. The study used descriptive statistics and ANOVA to treat the quantitative data and thematic analysis to treat the qualitative data.

Employment Status of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduates

Table 3 presents the employment rate of the BSBA graduates.

Table 3.
Employment rate of the BSBA graduates (N=79)

Employment Rate	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Employed	72	91.14
Unemployed	7	8.86

The survey shows that 91.14% of respondents were employed, which indicates that a high percentage of graduates are successful in finding jobs in the business field. However, 8.86% of respondents were unemployed, which indicates that a small percentage of graduates are still seeking employment or have their reasons for being unemployed.

Based on the information presented in Table 3, the high employment rate of 91.14% is a positive indication for graduates of the BSBA degree. It suggests that the business field offers a high demand for professionals, and graduates with this degree have good job prospects (Buenviaje et al., 2015). However, the small percentage of graduates who are still unemployed suggests that competition for jobs may still be high, and graduates need to differentiate themselves and develop a solid skillset to succeed in the job market (Lannu & Nobleza, 2017).

Matrix 1 presents the reason for the unemployment of BSBA graduates.

Matrix 1.

Reason of unemployment according to the respondents (N=7).

Reason for Unemployment	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Family Concern	2	28.57
Still Applying	2	28.57
Advance or Further Studies	1	14.29
Health Concern	1	14.29
Did not look for a job	1	14.29

As presented in Matrix 1, there are a variety of reasons why BSBA graduates may be unemployed. Family concerns may limit their ability to find a job (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020). Some graduates may still be applying for positions and have yet to secure employment (Lannu & Nobleza, 2017). Others may seek further education or career advancement opportunities that require additional time and investment (Meñez, 2014). Health concerns may also limit their ability to find employment (Castilla et al., 2022). Finally, some graduates may choose not to actively seek employment for personal reasons (Castillo, 2009). Matrix 1 further explains the unemployment results in Table 3.

Table 4 presents the employment status of the BSBA graduates.

Table 4.

Employment status of the BSBA graduates (N=72).

Employment Status	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Permanent	26	36.11
Casual	20	27.78
Self-Employed	18	25.00
Contractual	8	11.11

Based on the data in Table 4, the percentages show that most respondents have permanent or casual employment status. This implies more opportunities for graduates with a business administration degree in these types of employment (Buenviaje et al., 2015; Refozar et al., 2017). However, 25% have self-employment status, which may suggest that some graduates have chosen to start their businesses or pursue entrepreneurial ventures. This could be an opportunity for the business administration program to provide more support and education for students interested in

entrepreneurship (Roxas, 2012; Chienwattanasook & Jermstittiparsert, 2019). Additionally, the relatively small percentage of respondents with a contractual status of employment may indicate that graduates of the program are securing short-term contracts or project-based work to gain work experience (Llenares et al., 2021).

Matrix 2 presents the line of business of the BSBA graduates.

Matrix 2.

Line of work of the BSBA graduates (N=72)

Line of Work	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Wholesale, Retail Trade, Repair of Motor Vehicles, Motorcycles, Personal & Household Goods	31	43.06
Other Community, Social and Personal Service Activities	17	23.61
Financial Intermediation	11	15.27
Education	9	12.50
Real Estate, Renting Business Activities	2	2.78
Hotel & Restaurant	1	1.39
Health & Social Work	1	1.39

The data presented in Matrix 2 shows that a significant proportion of the respondents, i.e., 43.06%, work in wholesale or retail, followed by 23.61% who work in community, social, and personal services activities, and 15.27% in financial intermediation. This indicates that the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration graduates are in high demand in these sectors (Refozar et al., 2017). Moreover, the data also shows that a small proportion of the respondents are employed in real estate or renting businesses, hotels and restaurants, and health and social services. This implies there may be less demand for business graduates in these sectors (Pajares et al., 2018).

Table 5 presents the duration of the BSBA graduates in their current job.

Table 5.

Duration of the BSBA graduates in their job (N=72).

Duration	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Less Than a Month	2	2.78
1 To 6 Months	8	11.11
7 To 11 Months	10	13.89
1 Year to Less Than 2 Years	24	33.33
2 Years to Less Than 3 Years	12	16.67
3 Years to Less Than 4 Years	11	15.28
4 Years and Above	5	6.94

Based on Table 5, the graduates are experiencing varying durations of job tenure. This indicates a diverse employment landscape for BSBA graduates (Deblois, 2021). The percentage of respondents who have worked in their jobs for less than a month (2.78%) suggests that some graduates may struggle to find stable employment immediately after graduation (Tadlas, 2021). The percentage of graduates who have worked in their jobs for 1 to 6 months (11.11%) indicates that a significant portion of graduates experience early career growth and can secure employment relatively quickly after graduation (Laguador & Dotong, 2013). This suggests that the program

may equip graduates with the necessary skills and knowledge to enter the job market successfully (Diokno & Peprah, 2021).

The percentage of respondents who have worked in their jobs for 7 to 11 months (13.89%) implies that many graduates can sustain employment and progress beyond the initial stages of their careers (Mina et al., 2020). This demonstrates these individuals' potential for career advancement and stability (Rapoport, 2013). The percentage of respondents who have worked in their job for less than two years (33.33%) implies that a significant proportion of graduates can retain their jobs for a reasonable duration, indicating a level of employment stability for the first couple of years after graduation (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020).

Approximately 16.67% of the respondents have worked for less than three years, suggesting that many graduates may need help finding long-term career opportunities (Lannu & Nobleza, 2017). Moreover, 15.28% of the respondents have worked for less than four years, indicating that a substantial portion of BSBA graduates can secure stable employment in their initial years (Buenviaje et al., 2015). On a positive note, 6.94% of the participants have worked for more than four years, indicating that some graduates have successfully established long-term careers. This subgroup can provide valuable insights into factors contributing to their longevity in the job market (Coetzee et al., 2015). Generally, the percentages of respondents who have worked in their job for less than three years (16.67%), less than four years (15.28%), and more than four years (6.94%) suggest a mixture of career trajectories for graduates (Laguador & Dotong, 2013; Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020; Tadlas, 2021). While many graduates can establish longer-term employment, some may experience job turnover or other factors leading to shorter job durations (Supangco, 2015).

Table 6 presents the job position of the BSBA graduates.

Table 6.
Job position of the BSBA graduates (N=72).

Job Position	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Rank or Clerical	27	37.50
Professional, Technical or Supervisory	22	30.56
Management or Executive	5	6.94
Self-Employed	18	25.00

Based on Table 6, 37.5% of the respondents have rank or clerical job positions, which suggests that many BSBA graduates are employed in administrative or support roles. 30.56% have professional, technical, or supervisory job positions, indicating that many graduates have advanced to managerial or specialized roles. 6.64% having managerial or executive job positions implies a smaller percentage of graduates have reached high-level management positions in organizations (Buenviaje et al., 2015; Dotong et al., 2016). Moreover, 25% being self-employed implies that a quarter of the graduates have chosen to start their businesses or work as entrepreneurs, potentially showcasing their ability to apply their business knowledge to create opportunities (Roxas, 2012).

The data suggests that BSBA graduates can find employment in various positions across different sectors (Laguador & Dotong, 2013). It showcases that the skills acquired during the program can be applied in various roles, ranging from administrative to managerial positions

(Dionko & Peprah, 2021). The percentage of self-employed graduates indicates that entrepreneurship options are viable for these graduates, possibly due to their business knowledge and skills (Chienwattanasook & Jermsittiparsert, 2019).

Table 7 presents the location of work of the BSBA graduates.

Table 7.
Location of work of the BSBA graduates (N=72).

Location	f	%
Bukidnon Province	68	94.44
Outside Bukidnon Province	3	4.16
Abroad	1	1.39

Based on Table 7, the study reveals that the majority (94.44%) of BSBA graduates work within the Bukidnon province. This suggests that the program effectively produces professionals readily employed locally (Montales et al., 2020; Deblois, 2021). However, 4.16% and 1.39% of the respondents work outside the province and abroad, respectively. This could indicate a possible strong local business network, job demand in the region, or the presence of industries related to the field (Garcia & Casiro, 2019; Tantoy, 2019)

Table 8 presents the BSBA graduates' initial gross income.

Table 8.
Initial gross income of the of the BSBA graduates (N=72).

Initial Gross Income	f	%
Below ₱ 5,000.00	2	2.78
₱ 5,000.00 – ₱ 9,999.99	21	21.17
₱ 10,000.00 – ₱ 14,999.99	28	38.88
₱ 15,000.00 – ₱ 19,999.99	14	19.44
₱ 20,000.00 – ₱ 24,999.99	2	2.78
₱ 25,000.00 and above	5	6.94

The distribution of salaries among the respondents to understand the range and spread of salaries for BSBA graduates. By examining the percentages provided in Table 8, the proportion of graduates falling into various salary brackets. The percentages indicate that a substantial portion of the respondents (21.17%) earn less than ₱10,000.00. This suggests that entry-level job opportunities for BSBA graduates may have comparatively lower salaries (Beerepoot & Hendriks, 2013; Beam & Quimbo, 2021). The fact that only a tiny percentage (6.64%) of respondents earn salaries greater than ₱25,000.00 indicates a significant salary disparity among BSBA graduates. This could mean that most graduates face challenges securing higher-paying positions or career advancement (Roberto et al., 2022). Moreover, the result indicates that most BSBA graduates are not earning high salaries (Errighi et al., 2016).

Graduate Skills of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduates

Table 9 presents the BSBA graduates' assessment of the graduate skills of the course program.

Table 9.
BSBA graduates' assessment on the graduate skills.

Graduate Skill	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Int.
Communication Skills	4.15	0.856	A great extent
Human Relation Skills	3.89	0.875	A great extent
Entrepreneurial Skills	3.73	0.922	A great extent
Marketing Management Skills	3.40	0.799	A moderate extent
Problem-solving Skills	3.37	0.918	A moderate extent
Critical-thinking Skills	3.32	0.855	A moderate extent

Based on the information in Table 9, the study's respondents have reported relatively high scores in communication, human relations, and entrepreneurial skills. In contrast, their scores for marketing management skills, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking skills are slightly lower but still to a moderate extent. The result in Table 9 indicated that communication skills appear to be a strong suit for the graduates, with a mean score of 4.15 (± 0.856). This suggests that the program has developed the graduates' ability to convey information effectively (Deblois, 2021). Moreover, the human relation skills also received a high mean score of 3.89 (± 0.875). This indicates that the graduates possess strong interpersonal skills and can effectively work with others (Abulencia et al., 2021). Furthermore, the entrepreneurial skills also received a relatively high mean score of 3.73 (± 0.992). This implies that the graduates have the knowledge and mindset required to identify and exploit business opportunities (Roxas, 2014; Micabalo et al., 2022).

The respondents of the study have a moderate extent of marketing management skills, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking skills, with mean scores ranging from 3.40 (± 0.799), 3.37 (± 0.918), and 3.32 (± 0.855), respectively. This implies that graduates of the BSBA program have a satisfactory level of competency in these areas (Dotong et al., 2016). They possess the necessary skills to perform moderately well in marketing management, problem-solving, and critical thinking tasks (Muñez, 2014). However, the interpretation of "moderate extent" suggests that there is still room for improvement. The mean scores indicate a decent level of competency, but there might be scope for graduates to enhance their skills further in these areas (Laguador et al., 2020). Additionally, graduates should focus on further developing their skills in marketing management, problem-solving, and critical thinking to enhance their career prospects and succeed in the business field (Cruz & Nuqui, 2014; Abas & Imam, 2016; Bacani & Pizarro, 2022).

Table 10 compares the graduate skills as rated by the BSBA graduates.

Table 10.
Comparison of the graduate skills.

Graduate Skill	Mean	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Communication Skills	4.15 a		
Human Relation Skills	3.89 ab		
Entrepreneurial Skills	3.73 b	19.794	0.002*
Marketing Management Skills	3.40 bc		
Problem-solving Skills	3.37 bc		
Critical-thinking Skills	3.32 c		

NOTE: ** - Significant at 0.01

Exploring the Professional Trajectories of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduates of San Isidro College: An In-Depth Tracer Study

As presented in Table 9, the f -value of the six (6) graduate skills is 19.794, with a p -value of 0.002 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that there is a significant difference between the six (6) graduate skills. Additionally, Table 9 illustrates that communication skills have a higher level than other skills. Problem-solving skills and critical-thinking skills are at a lower level than the other six (6) graduate skills.

The tracer result highlights the disparity between communication and problem-solving/critical thinking skills among BSBA graduates. The results quantify the extent to which communication skills are higher than problem-solving and critical thinking skills, helping to understand the magnitude of the difference. The result implies that the BSBA program may focus more on communication skills, effectively integrating them into the curriculum. Effective communication skills are highly valued in various industries (Deblois, 2021).

Problem-solving and critical thinking are crucial for adapting to the rapidly changing business environment (Williams, 2002). However, graduates with only moderate skills in these areas may struggle and need help to keep up with industry advancements and innovative practices. As a result, they may be less likely to be promoted or considered for leadership roles that require advanced problem-solving and critical-thinking skills (Cruz & Nuqui, 2014; Abas & Imam, 2016).

Suggested Improvement of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration towards the Programs' Curriculum

Matrix 3 presents the suggestions of the BSBA graduates to improve the programs' curriculum.

Matrix 3.

Suggestions from the graduates towards the programs' curriculum (N=79)

Line of Work	f	%
Offer more course programs suitable for each major course.	21	26.58
Develop partnership with companies for Job Fairs.	20	25.32
Develop partnership with companies for OJT Programs.	15	18.99
Provide students with more trainings and seminars.	12	15.19
No Response	11	13.92

Based on the suggestions presented in Matrix 3, 26.58% of the respondents suggested offering more course programs suitable for each major course, indicating a need for diversity and specialization in business administration. Graduates may benefit from a broader range of courses that cater to specific industries or specialties within business administration (Ignatskaya, 2016).

Moreover, the suggestions of 25.32% of the respondents to develop partnerships with companies for job fairs and 18.99% for on-the-job training programs highlight the importance of industry connections for graduates. This implies that graduates may benefit from networking opportunities, internships, and job placement services to gain practical experience and secure employment in their field (Castro, 2014; Lacaden, 2015; Magnaye & Ylagan, 2021).

Furthermore, the suggestion of 15.19% of the respondents to provide students with more training and seminars reflects the desire for continuous learning and professional development among graduates. It suggests that graduates value lifelong learning opportunities and skill

enhancement to stay competitive and adapt to the ever-changing business landscape (Ylagan, 2013; Buenviaje et al., 2015).

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

The graduates of the BSBA can use this information to make informed decisions about their career choices. They can focus on seeking employment opportunities in the sectors with higher demand or adapt their skills and knowledge to fit the needs of the sectors with lesser demand. Additionally, the college can use this data to tailor their business programs to meet the industry demand better and ensure that graduates are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge for the job market.

Since no respondents identified as Business Economics majors, evaluating and modifying the curriculum, revamping marketing efforts, or exploring additional opportunities to create awareness and generate interest in this field among potential students might be necessary. Given the moderate level of interest and enrollment in Financial Management, it may be beneficial to continue marketing and highlighting the advantages and potential career prospects associated with this major. This can attract more students and ensure adequate representation in the program. Considering the high level of interest and enrollment in Human Resource Management, the college should continue to invest in this major, ensuring the program's quality is maintained and providing students with relevant skills and knowledge for their future careers.

The lower interest and enrollment rate in Marketing necessitates reviewing the program's curriculum and content, promotional efforts, and potential alignment with industry demands. Engaging with industry experts, considering internships or practical training opportunities, and actively promoting the benefits and career prospects of pursuing a marketing major to increase enrollment in this field would be advisable. Overall, the recommendations focus on addressing the need for more interest in Business Economics, strengthening the Financial Management and Marketing programs, and maintaining the positive momentum in the Human Resource Management major.

The job duration in the tracer study for the BSBA program indicates a mix of employment outcomes for graduates, including both early career growth and opportunities for long-term employment. The BSBA program equips graduates with a diverse skillset that enables them to secure positions in different job levels and industries. The program prepares graduates for various opportunities, including administrative, managerial, technical, supervisory, or entrepreneurial positions. The result indicates that the program has the potential to produce business professionals who can adapt to various job positions and industries.

Most graduates find employment within Bukidnon, indicating the potential for career growth and opportunities in the local job market. The high employment rate within the province implies that the BSBA program effectively equips students with the necessary skills and knowledge local employers seek. Although the high employment rate within the province is a positive indicator, efforts should be made to enhance the program's reputation and relevance outside the province to provide more opportunities for graduates.

The result of the distribution of salaries among the respondents to understand the range and spread of salaries for BSBA graduates fall into various salary brackets. The BSBA graduates earn

Exploring the Professional Trajectories of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduates of San Isidro College: An In-Depth Tracer Study

below minimum wage, indicating potential issues with the job market or the degree's value. The result necessitates further investigation and consideration of factors such as industry trends, job market conditions, and the quality of the BSBA program in order to provide a comprehensive understanding of the findings.

The BSBA program has successfully developed graduates with decent communication, human relations, and entrepreneurial skills. The program may need to focus more on enhancing graduates' marketing management, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills to ensure they meet industry standards. Considering the moderate mean scores for marketing management, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills, further evaluation or enhancement of the curriculum may be necessary to better equip graduates in these areas.

The tracer study concludes that BSBA graduates possess higher communication skills but comparatively lower problem-solving and critical-thinking skills. The findings call for curriculum adjustments to ensure a balanced development of the graduate skills for BSBA students. Moreover, the tracer study highlights the need for additional support or training for BSBA graduates to enhance their problem-solving and critical-thinking skills. Furthermore, the result highlights the importance of providing BSBA graduates with opportunities to enhance their problem-solving and critical thinking abilities to improve their overall graduate skills.

REFERENCE

- Abas, M. C., & Imam, O. A. (2016). Graduates' Competence on Employability Skills and Job Performance. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, *5*(2), 119-125.
- Abulencia, A. S., Marasigan, A. C., Raymundo, M. C. Y., Gomez, M. A. C., Aggarao, M. L. B., Bailon, J. V., ... & Sabate, R. (2021). Philippine Normal University Alumni Tracer Study. *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, *3*(5), 55-64.
- Albina, A. C., & Sumagaysay, L. P. (2020). Employability tracer study of Information Technology Education graduates from a state university in the Philippines. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, *2*(1), 100055. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100055>
- Bacani, J. D., & Pizarro, J. B. (2022). Integrated Industry-Based Academic Model for Marketing Education: A Value Innovation for St. Paul University Philippines. *Global Research Review in Business and Economics [GRRBE]*, *8*(1), 32-37.
- Badiru, E. O., & Wahome, M. (2016). Conducting Graduate Tracer Studies for Quality Assurance in East African Universities: A Focus on Graduate Students Voices on Quality Culture. *Journal of Education and Practice*, *7*(6), 174-181.
- Beam, E. A., & Quimbo, S. (2021). The Impact of Short-Term Employment for Low-Income Youth: Experimental Evidence from the Philippines. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 1-45. https://doi.org/10.1162/rest_a_01135
- Beerepoot, N., & Hendriks, M. (2013). Employability of offshore service sector workers in the Philippines: opportunities for upward labour mobility or dead-end jobs?. *Work, employment and society*, *27*(5), 823-841.
- Buenviaje, M. G., del Mundo, G. V., Añonuevo, F., & Martinez, M. (2015). Employability of business and computer management graduates of one higher education institution in the Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, *3*(5), 63-71.
- Castilla, D., Andrade, K. A., Icot, A., Pitogo, M., Suarez, M. A. C., & Hintapan, R. (2022). Profile Of Unemployed Youth of Liloan, Cebu City, Philippines: Some Proposals. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, *4*(7), 2145-2154

- Castillo, P. J. (2009). Unemployment Threat of the Financial Crisis. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, 9(1), 41-45.
- Castro, E. A. G. (2014, February). *Industry participation in developing competencies for employment success: Learnings from a 3-year ojt program of a philippine higher education institution*. Widyatama International Seminar.
- Chienwattanasook, K., & Jermstittiparsert, K. (2019). Impact of entrepreneur education on entrepreneurial self-employment: a study from Thailand. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.17512/pjms.2019.19.1.08>
- Cruz, R. C., & Nuqui, A. V. (2014). Revisiting the Employability and Productivity of Nursing Graduates of La Consolacion University Philippines. *IJTEMT*, 12-26.
- Coetzee, M., Ferreira, N., & Potgieter, I. L. (2015). Assessing employability capacities and career adaptability in a sample of human resource professionals. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 13(1), 1-9. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC171238>
- Cuadra, L. J., Aure, M. R. K. L., & Gonzaga, G. L. (2019). The use of tracer study in improving undergraduate programs in the university. *Asia Pacific Higher Education Research Journal (APHERJ)*, 6(1).
- Deblois, E. C. (2021). The employment profile of graduates in a state university in Bicol Region, Philippines. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*, 1(1), 33-41. <https://doi.org/10.52631/jemds.v1i1.10>
- Diokno, C. O. B., & Pephrah, W. K. (2021). Application of Technical and Soft Skills in the First Job Experience by Accountancy Graduates in the Philippines: Implications for Accounting Curriculum Development. *Open Journal of Accounting*, 10(3), 111-124. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojacct.2021.103010>
- Dotong, C. I., Chavez, N. H., Camello, N. C., De Castro, E. L., Prenda, M. T. B., & Laguador, J. M. (2016). Tracer study of engineering graduates of one higher education institution in the philippines for academic year 2009-2012. *European Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 4(4), 26-39.
- Errighi, L., Khatiwada, S., & Bodwell, C. (2016). *Business process outsourcing in the Philippines: Challenges for decent work*. ILO Asia-Pacific Working Paper Series.
- Garcia, K. B., & Casiro, R. B. C. (2019, August). *The Political Development of Valencia City, Bukidnon: A Historical Survey*. In International Conference on Public Organization (ICONPO).
- Hazaymeh, E. N., & Dela Peña, M. K. (2017). *A tracer study of La Salle University College of Engineering graduates*, 18(1), 52-68.
- Ignatskaya, M. A. (2016). Modern educational technologies: role and place of transdisciplinary cases (public and business administration specialization). *RUDN Journal of Public Administration*, (2), 35-49.
- Lacaden, C. C. (2015). Strategic Business Administration Program Model for Private Higher Education Institutions in the Philippines. *UNP Research Journal*, 24(1).
- Laguador, J. M., & Dotong, C. I. (2013). Tracer study of BS computer engineering graduates of Lyceum of the Philippines University. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 3(8), 387-401.
- Laguador, J. M., Chavez-Prinsipe, N. H., & De Castro, E. L. (2020). Employability skill development needs of engineering students and employers' feedback on their internship performance. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(7), 3097-3108. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080738>
- Lannu, J. E., & Nobleza, M. F. L. (2017). The Impact of Competitiveness on The Employability of Philippines Industrial Designers: Streamlining the Program with the International Market. *International Journal of Business & Administrative Studies*, 3(1).
- Llenares, I. I., Deocarís, C. C., & Deocarís, C. C. (2021). Work values of Filipino college students. *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling*, 49(4), 513-523. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03069885.2021.1939267>

Exploring the Professional Trajectories of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Graduates of San Isidro College: An In-Depth Tracer Study

- Magnaye, R. P., & Ylagan, A. P. (2021). Effectiveness and impact of community extension program of one Philippine Higher Education Institution as basis for sustainability. *Asia Pacific Journal of Academic Research in Business Administration*, 7(1).
- Meñez, N. L. (2014). Tracer study of the Masters in Business Administration (MBA) graduates from 2008-2012. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 1(1), 14-18.
- Micabalo, K. G., Atillo, L. A., & Abella, I. (2022). Implications Of Curriculum Design to Entrepreneurial Ability a Graduate Tracer Study. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Development (AJMRD)*, 4(06), 64-72.
- Mina, J. C., Reyes, E. J. G., & Salas, R. F. (2020). A tracer study of bachelor of science in information technology (BSIT) graduates of nueva ecija university of science and technology (NEUST), San Isidro campus. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, 5(4), 1337-1344. <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijels.54.77>
- Montales, J. A. P., Garcia, H. P., & Saniel, D. M. T. (2020). Correlational Analysis between Competencies Acquired by Business Education Graduates and Required by the Financial Industry. *Liceo Journal of Higher Education Research*, 16(2).
- Pajares, G. G., Bongcales, M., Roda, L., Villeta, R., Yadao, M., Avenido, J., ... & Susada, J. (2018). The sectoral and skills mismatch between the senior high school program and the top in-demand jobs and projected in-demand jobs in the province of Cebu, Philippines. *Researchers World. Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce*, 9(2), 187-199. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18843/rwjasc/v9i2/24>
- Pentang, J. T., Perez, D. R., Cuanan, K. H., Recla, M. B., Dacanay, R. T., Bober, R. M., ... & Nur-aina, A. (2022). Tracer study of teacher education graduates of Western Philippines University-Puerto Princesa Campus: Basis for curriculum review and revision. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(3), 419-432. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.03.12>
- Rapoport, R. N. (Ed.). (2013). *Mid-career development: research perspectives on a developmental community for senior administrators*.
- Refozar, R. F., Velasquez, J. E., & Luistro, E. J. (2017). Employability of BS Business and Computer Management Graduates from 2013 to 2015 in one Academic Institution in the Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Academic Research in Business Administration*, 3(3), 1-9.
- Roberto, V. A. B., Vivas, P. R. T., Yu, P. N. G., & Camaro, P. J. C. (2022). The Impact of Entrepreneurship and Unemployment to Income Inequality in the Philippines. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 5(11), 99-110.
- Roxas, B. (2014). Effects of entrepreneurial knowledge on entrepreneurial intentions: a longitudinal study of selected South-east Asian business students. *Journal of Education and Work*, 27(4), 432-453. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2012.760191>
- Supangco, V. T. (2015). Explaining employee intentions to stay in organizations: The case of MBA students. *Journal of International Business Research*, 14(3), 83-96.
- Tadlas, M. (2021). Tracer Study of the School of Education Graduates of San Isidro College: Their Employability and Suggested Interventions. *School of Education Research Journal*, 2(1), 67-75. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17074703.v1>
- Tantoy, O. A. (2019). Implementation of Extension Projects of Bukidnon State University: Basis for Monitoring Scheme. *Liceo Journal of Higher Education Research*, 15(1).
- Ylagan, A. P. (2013). Intensifying the OJT program of the college of business administration, Lyceum of the Philippines University-Batangas. *E-International Scientific Research Journal*, 5(1), 220-220.
- Williams, S. (2002). *Making better business decisions: Understanding and improving critical thinking and problem solving skills*. Sage.